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FACTORS INFLUENCING THE ECONOMIC WORLD VIEW OF YOUTH

Abstract. It is the "human capital" that sustains and develops society. In today's market economy, there is a great need to study the competitiveness of the employee and his mobility, as well as his economic outlook. Therefore, this article analyzes the role of economic knowledge in human life, the needs of the employer in the labor market, the goals of economic education of young people.

Keywords: economic thinking, employer needs, Science, education, economic integration, market mechanism.

Radical transformations in Uzbekistan have led to an aggravation and contradictions between the new market requirements for an employee of his competitiveness and mobility, as well as the level of formation of his competence and competencies of an economic nature. As a result, there is a need to form an economic outlook in the future specialist, the basis of which is economic competence.

The main resource for the development of modern society is "human capital", which provides society with stability and progress. The need for highly qualified, competitive [1,7,8] specialists capable of making independent decisions in a rapidly changing world places special demands on a person and on educational institutions.

Everything that is the property of economic science is the result of a long development of economic theory, born on the basis of practical economic activity. The origin of economic thinking and the beginnings of economic knowledge on the basis of housekeeping refers to the period of the emergence of human civilization. The value of property in awakening the feeling of the owner is enormous. He cares

not only about preserving, but also about increasing, multiplying it, realizing his social significance. A civilized owner is able to "share" his wealth, providing jobs and earning opportunities.

A market economy is impossible without a variety of forms and types of ownership. Article 53 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides all forms of ownership with equal rights and the possibility of legal protection from the state. All this is taken into account in the process of training young people and their practical activities and works to form economic thinking.

One of the most important components of professional education of university students is economic education. With the emergence of a special socio-economic situation in the country, the transition to labor markets and the market of educational services, economic education is of particular relevance. There is a need to form a new economic position among students and, accordingly, a new style of thinking, economic, demanded by modern times [2,3,4].

In recent years, the labor market has changed significantly, the needs of enterprises - the main employers - are changing.

Integration of science, education and economy is one of the most important directions in ensuring the innovative development of Uzbekistan. "The role of education at the present stage of development of Uzbekistan is determined by the tasks of its transition to a democratic and rule of law state, to a market economy. Without modern science-intensive technologies and provision of innovations and innovations to the leading sectors of the economy and high-tech production, the further prosperity of Uzbekistan is not conceivable.

The need for economic knowledge in the transition to market relations is obvious. A particular person needs an understanding of the fundamentals of market mechanisms today, because without such an understanding, he not only wins, but loses, not being guided by these mechanisms.

At the same time, the goal of economic education of students is the formation of:

- value orientations and attitudes arising from economic knowledge and leading to the consolidation of society;

- competencies sufficient to guide behavior and protect the interests of each person in contact with various types of economic activity and economic institutions;

- own ideas and attitudes, allowing to adequately judge the events, actions of the authorities and economic agents.

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Summarizing the above, we can draw the following conclusions:

In fact, there is no education apart from the economy. Only a moral society is able to create a highly developed economy that can influence the formation of a spiritually developed person with modern economic thinking [5,6,9].

The solution of global universal problems (energy, raw materials, environmental) is largely determined by the level of spiritual and moral development of people. Spiritual and moral development directly affects the needs of people. So, with the growth of spiritual and moral principles, more elevated needs also appear, incl. striving for personal improvement, which leads to positive changes in the economy.

In later life, economic thinking will not only make it possible to successfully use economic levers, but also expand the boundaries of human activity, form a harmonious, socially active personality, able to bring their own aspirations and interests in line with the expectations and needs of society.

REFERENCES

1. А. Долгова. Полная и эффективная занятость молодежи – условие повышения конкурентоспособности страны / А. Долгова, И. Жукова // Человек и труд. 2017. №8.
2. Курапова О.А. Проблемы социальной адаптации молодежи к современным условиям рынка труда. Курапова О.А. // <http://www.SCTavolsu.ru>
3. Казакова Н.Е. Мониторинг в сфере дополнительного профессионального образования // Стандарты и мониторинг в образовании. – 2006.
4. Котлова А.С., Попова О.А. Адаптация персонала на предприятии в современных условиях // Экономика и менеджмент инновационных технологий. – 2014. – № 6.
5. Adilovich N.R., Sharifovna Y.N., Upashevna A.L., Vladimirovna T.S., Juraevna N.N. THE PHENOMENON OF FRIENDSHIP IN THE SOCIAL VIEWS OF EASTERN THINKERS // Journal of Critical Reviews, 2020. Т. 7. № 13. С. 4695-4698.
6. Samarov RS, Rakhmonov DA (2016) SOCIAL WORK ACTIVITY IN PROVIDING THE LIFE OF THE SOCIETY (FUNCTIONAL-STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS). // ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 07 (39): 14-16.
7. Nazarova Nilufar Juraevna. 2021. “THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN YOUTH SOCIAL ACTIVISM”. Archive of Conferences, October, 50-51. <https://conferencepublication.com/index.php/aoc/article/view/1584>.
8. Nazarova, N. J. (2020). Qualities Of Youth Competitiveness (Sociological Aspect). International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR), 6(3), 14-20.
9. Акбарова, Л. У., & Саидназирханова, Ш. С. (2017). ГЛАВНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ ВЫСОКОГО УРОВНЯ КАЧЕСТВА ЖИЗНИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ В РЕГИОНАХ. In МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ В МЕНЕДЖМЕНТЕ КАК ОСНОВА ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ ПРОБЛЕМ МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ (pp. 16-18).